

E-Procurement and Company Performance: A Quantitative Analysis of The Textile Industry of Pakistan

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Abstract

The current study investigated the impact of top management support (TMS), technological factors and information quality (IQ) on implementation of e-Procurement leading towards company performance (CP) in the textile sector of Pakistan. 202 SC professionals and executives have participated in the data collection based on nonprobability purposive sampling technique using a five-point Likert scale questionnaire. Moreover, PLS-SEM technique has been used for data analysis. The findings showed that the implementation of eProcurement is positively impacted by top management support, technological factors, and information quality. Additionally, it has been discovered that eProcurement implementation of eProcurement has a favorable impact on business performance. Companies should provide training for workers involved in e-Procurement in order to raise the quality of information used to evaluate and improve business performance. E-Procurement adoption can be affected by a number of factors, one of which is the skills of the staff.

Keywords: e-Procurement, Technology, Company Performance, Pakistan, PLS-SEM.

1. Introduction

Enterprises may now access new markets and clients outside their conventional borders through e-procurement, which has become a crucial component of corporate strategy in today increasingly connected world. AlNuaimi et al. (2021) define e-procurement as the process of purchasing goods and services using the internet or another kind of network. Supplier exchange is another name for an online marketplace where people may buy and sell goods and services. In order to optimize the procurement process and speed up its value, the system will centralize and simplify a company's interactions with its clients and any other

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parties involved in the value chain. It offers a range of cutting-edge methods designed to shorten the amount of time, energy, and money spent on the purchase process (Mavidis & Folinias, 2022).

In particular, e-Procurement has shown industrial companies how to increase the value of their current processes more efficiently. EDI, also known as e-Procurement, or electronic data interchange, was initially used in the 1980s. The electronic data interchange (EDI) between business partners was revolutionary when it was introduced (Chen et al., 2022). Companies no longer had to physically submit paperwork since they could do it electronically instead. EDI, which was substituted by email, allowed for the transmission and reception of purchase orders and invoices through call-forward networks between suppliers and customers. Organizations improved EDI by developing online vendor directories in the late 1990s (Masudin et al., 2021b).

The enhancement of company performance is a key necessity for organizations in today's changing business climate, thus many of Pakistani firms have recently been exploring process innovation or improvement to meet their performance goal. Metrics should be set for performance measurement since it is necessary for performance analysis (Memon et al., 2021). Performance assessment becomes equally vital in this situation since improving corporate performance is a must in the current competitive, dynamic, and online economy. E-Procurement helps to develop appropriate performance measurements and metrics while keeping the organization's characteristics in mind (Naeem, 2021). Making the proper judgments that complement one another in attaining an organization's overall goals and objectives is the main purpose of utilizing eProcurement at the strategic, tactical, and operational levels (Ibadat, 2021).

In both traditional and online purchases, there is always the possibility of experiencing supply risk. Market risk, fraud, and issues with price, output quality, and distribution are the forms of risk that arise most often in business. Compatibility concerns, including anti-corruption and policy adherence, occupy a significant percentage of the thoughts of procurement executives. Companies run the risk of suffering a loss in their long-term financial position if they continue to make such unrestrained expenditures. When the number of a firm's acquisitions exceeds its ability to sustain those acquisitions via either its material inventories or its capital expenditures, the company is in a vulnerable position (Hammadama & Ahmad, 2021). E-procurement has major challenges, one of the most crucial being the maintaining of relationships with suppliers. The whole process is difficult, beginning with choosing the best vendor and continuing with monitoring the performance of vendors and making sure there is a consistent supply of high-quality merchandise. The onboarding of suppliers does not mark the end of this vital process. Supply chain partners require ongoing support and direction as they conduct business with customers (Korbel et al., 2022).

Furthermore, user interface that is difficult to utilize is another great obstacle while using e-procurement. The user experience must closely mirror other business platforms that professional users are interacting with. End users are unlikely to adopt a system if it does not supply the necessary item or service, if pricing is not in line with agreed upon best value, if the approval process is too complex and time-consuming, or if the program is challenging to use (Berndt, 2022). Performance assessment of e-procurement systems has various obstacles, including: a lack of awareness of the advantages of performance measurement,

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indicators that are unrelated to organizational goals, and problems gathering data for performance measurement. Economic, cultural, and cognitive limitations, as well as sociopolitical and other impediments, are also the key obstacles to the adoption of e-procurement in developing nations (Rashid & Uddin, 2021).

Numerous studies have looked at the adoption of e-procurement by both public and commercial organizations during the past ten years but very little work is done in developing nations such as Pakistan. Moreover, experiential research on the use of e-procurement systems by public sector organizations in poor nations seems to be underutilized. This paper adds to the few but important studies of e-procurement in the context of manufacturing enterprises by examining e-procurement in the textile industry, which has not seen a lot of research in the service sector of Pakistan. The current study investigate the impact of top management support (TMS), technological factors and information quality (IQ) on implementation of e-Procurement leading towards company performance (CP) in the textile sector of Pakistan.

This study seeks to understand and identify the drivers, barriers, advantages, crucial success factors, organizational performance following implementation, and the impact of e-procurement usage in textile industry of Pakistan. Since, there is a significant lack of data in terms of implementation of e-procurement in emerging nation; therefore, this study will prove to be an important one. It does this through empirical research on the level of e-procurement adoption in Pakistan and how it impacts textile industries. The current study aims to investigate the impact of TMS and IQ on implementation of e-Procurement leading towards company performance.

The remaining paper will provide existing empirical information about the current topic and theoretical backdrop. The section will also include hypotheses proposed by the study. The third section of this study will examine the conceptualizing of the methodological aspects, including the rationale for selecting a specific research approach, research strategy, sampling and population. Additionally, it will provide an explanation of the data collection instrument and the techniques used for data analysis. The study's outcomes and conclusions are discussed in section four using statistical inference and descriptive analysis. This section explains the findings of the hypothesis-testing analysis using PLS-SEM. Discussions of these results will also be provided in the light of previous studies, in fifth section. Lastly, the paper will end with conclusion and practical recommendations are provided based on the results and lastly, limitations and future research will also be given.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Dynamic capabilities

Teece et al. (1997) were the ones that came up with the idea of dynamic capabilities. DC reflect an organization's capacity to adapt to and have an influence on the quickly changing business environment in which it operates by integrating, producing, or rearranging both internal and external assets, including expertise (Idries et al., 2022). According to one view, the growth of DC is fueled by strategic routines and competencies, integrated value chains, and sustainability-focused enhancements, but also judicious organizational advances are the key factors (Pigola et al., 2022). The current research relates to dynamic capabilities by investigating how factors like technology adoption, management support, and information

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quality influence a firm's ability to dynamically adapt its procurement processes. By enhancing these capabilities through e-Procurement, organizations can better respond to changing market conditions, fostering long-term competitiveness (Bari et al., 2022).

2.2. Organizational information processing theory

Jay Galbraith (1973) developed an OIPT in the context of organizations facing dynamic changes in their business environment (Wijewickrama et al., 2022). This theory focuses on the organizational design structure that an organization must establish to handle and cope with many types of uncertainty that may exist at any given time (Ali, 2022). According to OIPT, when uncertainty increases, information processing capacity must also increase to meet information demands (Yu et al., 2022). According to OIPT, the primary purpose of the structure of an organization is to minimize risk via the collection, analysis, and transmission of knowledge obtained from the external environment of the operations of the company. This represents the core aim of an organization's structure (Yu et al., 2019). The current study applies organizational information processing theory by examining how information quality impacts e-Procurement adoption and, subsequently, organizational performance. It aligns with the theory's focus on how organizations gather, process, and utilize information to make informed decisions, illustrating how information quality influences operational outcomes in the context of procurement (Ali, 2022).

2.3. Hypotheses Development

Due to their position within the organization, top management should oversee the company's organizational activities. An organization will follow the activities, instructions, and efforts of top management when determining the direction of corporate development. The main objective of top management support is to make it the main factor determining the success of a project (Masudin et al., 2021b). The primary resource allocator is senior management, which is responsible for overseeing the effective deployment of e-procurement for a variety of resources, including human resources (Susantya et al., 2022). Hence, it is hypothesized that;

H1. Top management support has a positive effect on implementation of e-Procurement.

The word "technological factors" relates to the practicability, interoperability, and practicability of the technology systems that are used inside businesses. The degree to which e-Procurement is adopted may significantly influenced by the capabilities and usability of the technology (Masudin et al., 2021b). A company's objectives, organizational structure, and operational procedures must all be compatible with e-Procurement (Yeboah, 2022). According to Susantya et al. (2022) organizations must design their systems to be interoperable with one another in order to avoid significant technological hurdles resulting from the integration of several standards. Among the most important characteristics of effective electronic procurement systems are standardization, transparency, interaction, accessibility, usability, privacy, and dependability. Effective communication between e-procurement systems and users is crucial (Xu et al., 2022). Hence, it is hypothesized that;

H2. Technological factors have a positive effect on implementation of e-Procurement.

The information technology platforms that are integrated with e-procurement have a significant impact on the data quality. E-procurement is growing more and more widespread

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in business operations, according to Atmaja and Sfenrianto (2021), due to the expansion of IT platforms. In a different research, Álvarez Rodríguez (2022) predicted that semantic technology will become more popular in e-Procurement applications (Masudin et al., 2021b). In a separate research, Kim et al. (2022) used the DeLone and McClean (D&M) information system success model in a different study to examine the factors influencing the data-sharing model that encourages the use of e-Procurement services. The results of their study indicate that the perceived advantages of e-Procurement are significantly impacted by the caliber of the information, system, and services provided. Hence, it is hypothesized that;

H3. Information quality has a positive effect on implementation of e-Procurement.

The industry's state within a given time period is thoroughly presented in the corporate profitability. It is the outcome of success impacted by the operational activities the company engages in while employing its resources. Efficiency, sales results, customer happiness, and connection building all contribute to a company's performance (Masudin et al., 2021b). After taking part in e-procurement, a company's performance, including efficiency, sales performance, customer happiness, and relationship development, get improved. According to earlier research by Monteiro et al. (2022), a company's success depends on its ability to satisfy its customers. Marketers, customers, consumers, and customer behavior researchers are the groups most closely connected to customer satisfaction or discontent. Customers have the opportunity to select the highest quality due to producer competition, increasing their leverage in negotiations. Hence, it is hypothesized that;

H4. Implementation of e-Procurement has a positive effect on company performance.

As per Marei (2022), the implementation of e-Procurement can mediate the effect of top management support on company performance by enhancing resource allocation, improving efficiency, reducing costs, and enabling data-driven decision-making. Top management support provides the necessary resources and strategic direction, while e-Procurement facilitates operational improvements and contributes to overall business performance through streamlined processes and enhanced financial control (Chebet & Kihara, 2022). Hence, it is hypothesized that;

H5. Implementation of e-Procurement positively mediates the effect of top management support on company performance.

The implementation of e-Procurement positively mediates the effect of technological factors on company performance by leveraging advanced technology to streamline procurement processes, enhance data accuracy, and facilitate cost-efficient operations, as stated in a recent study done by (Marei, 2022). In addition, this mediation bridges the gap between technology and improved performance, as e-Procurement systems optimize resource utilization and support informed decision-making, ultimately contributing to overall business success (Shatta, 2023). Hence, it is hypothesized that;

H6. Implementation of e-Procurement positively mediates the effect of technological factors on company performance.

Previous studies have noted that the implementation of e-Procurement positively mediates the effect of information quality on company performance by ensuring that high-quality, accurate data is readily available for decision-making (Chebet & Kihara, 2022; Idrees et al., 2022; Prianto & Setyadi, 2023). E-Procurement systems enhance data integrity, reduce errors, and improve information accessibility, enabling better-informed choices, streamlined

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operations, and ultimately, improved overall business performance (Safriandi et al., 2023). Hence, it is hypothesized that;

H7. *Implementation of e-Procurement positively mediates the effect of information quality on company performance.*

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

3. Methodology

This research has adopted a quantitative deductive research approach, explanatory research type, and correlational research design because it aims to analyze relationships and causal links between variables. Such an approach allows for the systematic collection and analysis of numerical data, helping to quantify the impact of factors like technology, management support, and information quality on e-procurement adoption and corporate performance. It provides a structured framework to test hypotheses and generate evidence-based explanations, contributing to a deeper understanding of the subject matter and enabling the identification of key influencing factors (Curtis et al., 2016; Seeram, 2019).

The textile industry is one of Pakistan's main industrial sectors. Pakistan is the eighth-largest textile exporter in Asia. 8.5% of Pakistan's GDP is accounted for by the textile industry (Quddoos et al., 2022). The researcher determined that it would be more appropriate to gather pertinent information from SC professionals and executives of the textile firms in Karachi, as they are regarded as the top management in every firm. Nonprobability purposive sampling was chosen for this study to specifically target and include experts and executives from Karachi's textile industries who possess the relevant knowledge and experience related to e-procurement, aligning with the study's focused research objectives (Etikan et al., 2016). Table 3.1 has showed the results of demographic profile of the respondents.

Table 3.1: Demographic Profile (n=202)

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	125	61.9
	Female	77	38.1
Academic Qualification	Undergraduate	7	3.5
	Graduate	96	47.5
	Postgraduate	86	42.6
	Others	13	6.4

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	< 250	49	24.3
Firm Size	250 to 500	65	32.2
	501 to 1000	47	23.3
	More than 1000	41	20.3
	Assistant Manager	56	27.7
Job Position	Manager	54	26.7
	Senior Manager	49	24.3
	Deputy Manager	43	21.3
	< 3 years	20	9.9
Professional Experience	3 to 7 years	105	52.0
	8 to 12 years	77	38.1

The primary objective of statistical surveys is to draw statistical inferences about the population under investigation. The accuracy and reliability of these inferences are strongly contingent upon the survey questions used. The current study has utilized face-to-face and online survey methodology of data collection. After collecting, the survey data is statistically analyzed to provide meaningful research findings (Groves et al., 2011). The survey questionnaire is developed using 5-point Likert scale denoting 1 as strongly disagree and 5 as strongly agree (Joshi et al., 2015). Table 3.1 shows the instrumentation and measurement of the variables with their sources.

Table 3.2:

Research instrumentation and measurement

Variable Name	N Items	Likert Type	Source(s)
Top management support	4	5-Point	(Lo et al., 2021)
Technological factors	5	5-Point	(Zulu, 2018)
Information quality	5	5-Point	(Sambasivan et al., 2010)
e-Procurement Implementation	6	5-Point	(MacManus, 2002)
Company performance	5	5-Point	(Chatzoglou & Diamantidis, 2009)

The current study will analyze data through PLS-SEM using SmartPLS v3. PLS-SEM evaluates how well the model accounts for the target constructs of interest by estimating the associations between the latent variables (Hair et al., 2019). In order to estimate large models with several constructs, structural routes and indicator variables without imposing distributional assumptions on the data, many researchers find the PLS-SEM technique to be particularly intriguing (Hair Jr et al., 2017). PLS-SEM, as opposed to regression, permits the incorporation of measurement error when dealing with the latent variables in these models (Hair et al., 2011), therefore the current researcher has chosen this particular data analysis

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technique.

4. Results

This is the fourth section of this paper and it will include all the details about how the data was analyzed and its results.

4.1. Measurement model

Table 4.1 shows the results of measurement model.

Table 4.1: Measurement Model

	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
FP2 <- Company Performance	0.848			
FP3 <- Company Performance	0.838	0.813	0.886	0.722
FP4 <- Company Performance	0.863			
IEP1 <- Implementation of e-Procurement	0.842			
IEP2 <- Implementation of e-Procurement	0.805			
IEP3 <- Implementation of e-Procurement	0.818	0.923	0.940	0.723
IEP4 <- Implementation of e-Procurement	0.869			
IEP5 <- Implementation of e-Procurement	0.868			
IEP6 <- Implementation of e-Procurement	0.894			
IQ2 <- Information Quality	0.907			
IQ3 <- Information Quality	0.925	0.874	0.920	0.794
IQ4 <- Information Quality	0.840			
TF1 <- Technological Factors	0.756			
TF2 <- Technological Factors	0.813			
TF3 <- Technological Factors	0.910	0.873	0.908	0.664
TF4 <- Technological Factors	0.801			
TF5 <- Technological Factors	0.788			
TMS2 <- Top Management Support	0.853			
TMS3 <- Top Management Support	0.930	0.864	0.917	0.787
TMS4 <- Top Management Support	0.876			

According to Hair et al. (2011), indicator loadings should be higher than 0.70 for construct validity; whereas, Hair et al. (2014) suggested that alpha should be higher than 0.70, CR should be higher than 0.80 and AVE should be higher than 0.50 for acceptable reliability and convergence of the constructs. Above table has shown that indicators and constructs have met these criteria and therefore, construct validity and convergent validity has been achieved.

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Figure 4.1: PLS Algorithm

4.2. Discriminant validity

Table 4.2 shows the results of HTMT ratio for discriminant validity.

Table 4.2: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	CP	IEP	IQ	TF	TMS
Company Performance					
Implementation of e-Procurement	0.712				
Information Quality	0.519	0.638			
Technological Factors	0.796	0.747	0.493		
Top Management Support	0.785	0.810	0.755	0.776	

Henseler et al. (2015) suggested that discriminant validity can be achieved when the HTMT ratios are found below than 0.85 for substantial divergence between latent constructs. Above table has met this criterion and therefore, discriminant validity using HTMT ratio had been achieved.

4.3. Structural model

Table 4.3 and 4.4 shows the results of path analysis of direct and indirect hypotheses results.

Table 4.3: Path Analysis

	Estimate	S. D.	t-Stats	Prob.
Top Management Support -> Implementation of e-Procurement	0.351	0.072	4.840	0.000
Technological Factors -> Implementation of e-Procurement	0.355	0.064	5.526	0.000
Information Quality -> Implementation of e-Procurement	0.205	0.055	3.737	0.000

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Implementation of e-Procurement -> Company Performance	0.648	0.037	17.452	0.000
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The above table shows that top management support ($\beta = 0.351, p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on implementation of e-Procurement. Technological factors ($\beta = 0.355, p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on implementation of e-Procurement. Information quality ($\beta = 0.205, p < 0.05$) also has a positive and significant effect on implementation of e-Procurement. Implementation of e-Procurement ($\beta = 0.648, p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on company performance.

Table 4.4: Mediation Analysis

	Estimate	S. D.	t-Stats	Prob.
Top Management Support -> Implementation of e-Procurement -> Company Performance	0.227	0.049	4.605	0.000
Technological Factors -> Implementation of e-Procurement -> Company Performance	0.230	0.046	5.000	0.000
Information Quality -> Implementation of e-Procurement -> Company Performance	0.133	0.037	3.593	0.000

Above table has shown that implementation of e-procurement ($\beta = 0.227, p < 0.05$) positively mediates the effect of top management support on company performance. Moreover, implementation of e-procurement ($\beta = 0.230, p < 0.05$) positively mediates the effect of technological factors on company performance. Lastly, implementation of e-procurement ($\beta = 0.133, p < 0.05$) positively mediates the effect of information quality on company performance.

Figure 4.2: PLS Bootstrapping

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5. Discussions

According to a recent research, the implementation of e-Procurement is influenced favorably by top management support. This view is supported by Susantya et al. (2022), who state that top-level management agreement is essential since it may have an adverse effect on a variety of HR-related factors. In order to assure the effective implementation of e-Procurement, senior management, the principal resource allocator, may allocate a number of resources, including human resources (Marei, 2022). The top management of the organization must understand that the primary objective of e-procurement is to facilitate a quicker and more efficient procurement process. These findings corroborate study by Chebet and Kihara (2022), who found that the modeling of the implementation plan and a comprehensive set of activities were made possible by senior management assistance. The business effectively utilizes outside resources to market the project.

Current study had also found that technological factors have a positive effect on implementation of e-Procurement. Technological factors aids in improvement of the organizational structure, and operational procedures of a corporation which must be compatible with e-procurement (Yuslinda et al., 2022). Companies design their systems to be interoperable with one another in order to avoid significant technological hurdles caused by the integration of several requirements as claimed by Salifu et al. (2022). Additionally, users must be able to interface with e-procurement systems, Yeboah (2022) suggested. However, it has been determined that the main challenge that has to be removed before e-procurement can be properly implemented is a lack of strategic linkage across the various e-government platforms using proper technological factors (Susantya et al., 2022).

Current study had also found that information quality has a positive effect on implementation of e-Procurement. The deployment of e-procurement is significantly impacted by information quality. Ramadhani et al. (2022), who asserts that IQ is used to characterize e-commerce (online) issues, supports it as well. The success of electronic procurement depends on web-based applications being comprehensive, relevant, easy to use, and customized. Additionally, they must ensure that the targeted customers or suppliers carry out online transactions. Perceived risk, trust, and ease of use are the three characteristics that Chebet and Kihara (2022) claims make up the service quality dimension. Supplier involvement is closely related to the use of electronic procurement. Even if all transactions are conducted online, it's critical to retain mutual trust between suppliers and buyers while implementing e-procurement (internet). Haryono (2022) claims that through usability and user happiness, information quality significantly influences views in favor of implementing e-procurement.

Current study had concluded that implementation of e-Procurement has a positive effect on CP. Wijaya (2022) agrees, claiming that by improving the efficiency of the procurement operations and successfully addressing customer needs, the usage of e-procurement increases competitive advantage. This is supported by Chebet and Kihara (2022), achieving optimal CP is the fundamental goal. Hence, any changes to technology or methods must improve the organization's performance. E-procurement helps to streamline the purchasing process and affects the company's financial and non-financial performance (Singh & Chan, 2022).

Current study has found that implementation of e-Procurement positively and significantly mediates between top management support and company performance. Procurement

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department transparency and effectiveness would increase with e-Procurement, which would assist top management and improve overall performance of company. Masudin et al. (2021b) found a similar result. Moreover, senior management makes decisions on the distribution of firm resources and the process is facilitated through e-procurement. Management may commit plenty of human resources to help with organizational environment projects. Senior management is in charge of allocating resources effectively and is in charge of ensuring that e-procurement is used for a range of resources, including human resources (Chebet & Kihara, 2022). Current study has found that implementation of e-Procurement significantly mediates between technological factors and company performance. It's feasible that the effectiveness and usability of the technology is significantly affected by how broadly e-procurement is used. Implementation of e-Procurement makes technology compatible with the objectives, organizational structure, and operational procedures of a corporation as concluded by Masudin et al. (2021b). Companies that design their systems to be interoperable with one another in order to avoid significant technological hurdles caused by the integration of several specifications and in turn improves their overall performance (Marei, 2022).

Current study has found that implementation of e-procurement mediates between information quality and company performance. The quality of the information is crucial when it comes to adoption of e-procurement, as has been shown in earlier studies (Masudin et al., 2021a). The efficiency of the logistical fulfilment process, the information flow process, and customer satisfaction with e-Procurement are all significantly interconnected (Chebet & Kihara, 2022). Previous studies have shown the quality of the information, and the communication system have a significant impact on the perceived benefits of implementing e-procurement (Haryono, 2022).

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1. Recommendations

Based on empirical findings, top management should assess their readiness for efficient e-procurement utilization, acknowledging the need to address resource inertias. Managers should familiarize themselves with conceptual models to make informed choices, recognizing the impact of e-procurement decisions on B2B operations. Ensuring favorable IS implementation effects on company performance is crucial. To enhance information quality affecting business performance, firms should provide training to e-procurement staff, recognizing their role as a key variable. Allocating resources for comprehensive employee training in e-procurement systems is essential, especially when adopting new technology.

Selecting the appropriate technology or platform is vital for e-procurement success. Senior internal management should make these resources available, considering factors like risk, future trends, efficacy, and costs. Tailoring technology choices to the needs of users and utilizing metrics such as the technological readiness index and technology acceptance model can aid in adoption and acceptance. Prior to procurement, textile company managers should conduct thorough market research to identify suitable suppliers and manufacturers. Prioritizing suppliers' accessibility, capabilities, pricing, and past performance data is essential for effective procurement strategies.

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6.2. Limitations and future research

This research has limitations, including a small Karachi-based sample, limiting comprehensive investigation, and data gathered through 5-point Likert scale survey. A shift to a seven-point Likert scale for more methodological precision is recommended. Findings are confined to Pakistani textile firms, reducing cross-national applicability. Future research should expand geographically, encompassing diverse textile enterprises within Karachi. The absence of moderator variables is another limitation. Resource constraints and financial limitations in Pakistan pose challenges. Broader data sources and budgets should be pursued, utilizing qualitative and quantitative methods. Verified data can also support future inquiries. Research avenues include exploring electronic technology in various business processes and incorporating additional mediating or moderating variables for a more comprehensive conceptual framework.

6.3. Conclusion

This study in Pakistan's textile industry explored the impact of technological advancements, top management support (TMS), and information quality (IQ) on e-Procurement adoption and corporate performance (CP). Using quantitative analysis, the study targeted supply chain (SC) experts and textile industry executives in Karachi. Results indicated that e-Procurement adoption benefits from top management support and is positively influenced by technology and information quality. Furthermore, e-Procurement implementation positively affects company performance. The study underscores the importance of information quality and senior management involvement in e-Procurement adoption, offering valuable insights for managers and policymakers in underdeveloped countries seeking to enhance procurement practices.

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